

Uzbekistan and the U.S. trade relations: Historical Development and Current State

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Abstract (English)

This article analyzes trade and economic relations between Uzbekistan and the United States, focusing on their current state, existing opportunities, and key challenges. The research is conducted in the context of economic reforms in Uzbekistan and the country's integration into the global economy. The findings show that although bilateral trade volumes remain relatively low, there is significant potential for expansion in textiles, agriculture, and services. At the same time, logistical difficulties, regulatory barriers, and market access issues continue to limit trade growth. The article offers recommendations to enhance bilateral trade cooperation.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, United States, bilateral trade, trade opportunities, trade challenges, economic cooperation

Annotatsiya (O'zbek tilida)

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston va AQSh o'rtasidagi savdo-iqtisodiy aloqalar, ularning hozirgi holati, mavjud imkoniyatlar va asosiy muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot O'zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlar va mamlakatning jahon iqtisodiyotiga integratsiyalashuvi sharoitida olib boriladi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni

ko'rsatadiki, ikki mamlakat o'rtasidagi savdo hajmi nisbatan past bo'lsa-da, to'qimachilik, qishloq xo'jaligi va xizmatlar sohasida katta salohiyat mavjud. Shu bilan birga, logistika muammolari, standartlar va bozorga kirishdagi to'siqlar savdo rivojlanishini cheklamoqda. Maqolada ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Аннотация (на русском языке)

В данной статье рассматриваются торгово-экономические отношения между Узбекистаном и Соединёнными Штатами Америки, их текущее состояние, возможности и основные проблемы. Исследование проводится в условиях экономических реформ в Узбекистане и его интеграции в мировую экономику. Результаты показывают, что несмотря на относительно небольшой объём двусторонней торговли, существует значительный потенциал для развития сотрудничества в текстильной, сельскохозяйственной и сервисной сферах. Вместе с тем логистические трудности, регуляторные барьеры и проблемы доступа на рынок сдерживают рост торговли. В статье предлагаются рекомендации по развитию торгового сотрудничества.

Introduction

In recent years, Uzbekistan has implemented large-scale economic reforms aimed at liberalizing foreign trade and improving the business environment. Since 2017, trade barriers have been reduced, the currency market has been liberalized, and support for private entrepreneurship has increased. As a result, Uzbekistan has become more open to international trade and cooperation.

The political and military relations between Uzbekistan and the United States was at the peak during the period of 2001 through 2005. At the initiative of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, the military airbase in southern Uzbekistan was leased out to the US for free use as a military base for its antiterrorist operations in

Afghanistan. This politico-military action of these two states was a Strategic Partnership and Cooperation and could be example for military cooperation or alliance.

According to the strategic partnership, the US military should have been involved in democratic reforms in Uzbekistan, assisted in economic development, market relations, invested in economic growth, boosting military capabilities of Uzbekistan, and jointly responding to the country's domestic and foreign security. However, some of the above conditions were not been fully implemented or led to the disintegration of the military regiment, and the study of this has become an important topic for deeper analysis of history.

It is important to study the sudden end of the strategic partnership and cooperation between Uzbekistan and the United States in 2005. Because the study of the reasons for the termination of the agreement can be useful in the future in the development and continuation of foreign relations of both countries. All factors that led to the termination of the strategic partnership and cooperation have not been thoroughly studied in any academic research. These factors have been deeply analyzed and learned in most studies: the sudden withdrawal of the US military base was largely due to the lack of democratic openness and development, a lack of protection of human rights in Uzbekistan, and the cut of economic assistance by the congress to Uzbekistan. The cut of economic assistance of the USA was one of important factors of the termination of the Strategic Partnership and Cooperation. But, in particular, economic relations between the United States and Uzbekistan, Russia and Uzbekistan, and China and Uzbekistan in 2001-2005 and importance of these ties have not been compared.

One of the key goals of Uzbekistan's trade policy is diversification. Previously, the country's foreign trade was mainly oriented toward regional partners. This created economic dependence and limited access to advanced markets. Therefore, cooperation with developed economies has become increasingly important.

The United States is one of the largest economies in the world and an important actor in global trade. Trade cooperation with the U.S. can provide Uzbekistan with access to new markets, advanced technologies, and modern business practices. However, despite positive political relations, trade volumes between Uzbekistan and the U.S. remain limited.

The president **Sh.Mirziyoyev** stressed that relations between Uzbekistan and the United States had reached an unprecedented level:

“Over the past eight years, trade turnover increased fourfold. More than 300 American companies have invested in Uzbekistan in critical minerals, finance, IT, pharmaceuticals and other sectors. We will create every condition for US businesses to feel confident in Uzbekistan and to fully benefit from the unique opportunities of our rapidly growing market.”

He noted that since reforms began in 2017, the Uzbek economy had doubled in size and continued to show steady growth:

“Major reforms have been carried out in the tax system. Business registration procedures were simplified. Hundreds of bureaucratic barriers were removed. Today, foreign investors are protected by law. As a result, annual foreign direct investment increased tenfold,” the president said.

The main purpose of this article is to analyze Uzbekistan–U.S. trade relations, identify opportunities and challenges, and propose recommendations for improving bilateral trade cooperation.

Literature Review

International trade theory provides the theoretical basis for analyzing bilateral trade relations. Classical economists such as Adam Smith and David Ricardo explained trade through absolute and comparative advantage. These theories suggest that countries benefit from specialization and trade based on productivity differences.

Later, the Heckscher–Ohlin model emphasized the role of factor endowments in shaping trade patterns. According to this approach, countries export goods that use abundant factors of production. However, this theory does not fully explain modern trade relations between countries with different levels of development.

Modern trade theories focus on economies of scale, technology, and institutional factors. Empirical studies on transition economies show that trade liberalization, regulatory reforms, and improved logistics play a key role in export growth.

Studies on Uzbekistan mainly analyze export diversification and integration into global markets. However, research specifically focused on Uzbekistan–U.S. trade relations is limited. This article aims to contribute to filling this gap.

Research Methodology

This study uses a qualitative and descriptive research methodology. The analysis is based on secondary data obtained from international organizations such as the World Bank, International Monetary Fund, OECD, and official trade statistics of Uzbekistan and the United States.

Several methods are applied in the research. Trend analysis is used to observe changes in trade dynamics over time. Comparative analysis helps to examine the structure of exports and imports. Institutional analysis is used to study trade regulations and policies affecting bilateral trade.

The data are considered reliable because they come from official and internationally recognized sources. However, the study is limited by the lack of detailed firm-level data.

Analysis and Results

For the United States, Uzbekistan was a springboard for penetration into Central Asia and for creating a zone of influence in the region in order to oust Russia and China. At the same time, the geopolitical significance of Central Asia and Uzbekistan was recognized by US leaders even before the September 11 incident.

After the terrorist attacks of 11 September, 2001, Uzbekistan was one of the first to express its support for the United States. It agreed to use its infrastructure for military purposes during the antiterrorist campaign in Afghanistan. At this time, the US and Uzbekistan developed close political relations, which was demonstrated in March 2002 during the visit of the President of Uzbekistan to Washington, where he met with George W. Bush and the signing of a strategic partnership agreement. Improvement of relations with Washington has brought great advantages to Uzbekistan. First of all, this made it possible to eliminate the influence of the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan, which became the greatest threat to the Republic. In addition, Uzbekistan becoming an "anchor" country for the United States in Central Asia, hoped for US investment in its economy, especially in the oil and gas sector. In addition, it was assumed that Tashkent's influence on Afghanistan would increase, and the southern borders of Uzbekistan would be safe.

After the events of September 11, **I.A. Karimov** said that the country is "ready to cooperate with the US in the fight against terrorism" (Ülkü, 2002). During the visit of US Secretary of Defense D. Rumsfeld to Tashkent on October 5, 2001, an agreement was signed on bilateral cooperation in the fight against terrorism. In a short, it was stated in a joint declaration that Uzbekistan gives the US agreed to use the airspace, as well as one of its airfields for "humanitarian operations" (Djalili & Kellner, 2009).

Thus, NATO and the US acquired a strategically important stronghold in Karshi-Khanabad, located in the southeast of Uzbekistan, near the Afghan border. This base has become the largest point of the US support in the region, where up to three thousand servicemen have been deployed. Later it became an instrument of restraining Russia (Lachowski, 2007). However, close ties did not last long. Human rights violations in Uzbekistan served as a pretext for their breakdown in 2004-2005.

Cooperation between the United States and Uzbekistan reached its peak in 2003. However, the project of the Greater Middle East, as well as the strategy of democratization in the region, including violently, aroused I.A. Karimov's fears. Tashkent's concern grew as the "color revolutions" were carried out with the help of the United States in the republics of the former Soviet Union.

In late 2003, Georgian President Eduard Shevardnadze tried to get closer to Russia, but was overthrown, and Mikhail Saakashvili, a politician dependent on the US, came to power during the Rose Revolution. This prompted the administration of I.A. Karimov to take decisive action. First of all, the activity of all foreign non-governmental organizations operating in Uzbekistan was limited (Genç, 2010). The activities of those organizations that carried a potential danger ceased. A number of events that occurred in 2004 created tensions between the US and Uzbekistan. Sometime after this, I.A. Karimov made a diplomatic maneuver and made an official visit to Moscow, during which it was decided to jointly fight terrorism.

Washington has always faced a dilemma in its relations with Uzbekistan: continue to support the authoritarian administration in accordance with its strategic interests, or abide by the declared principles of freedom and democracy.

In 2013 the USA has offered to Uzbekistan various investment projects totaling \$4 billion. As a result both I. A. Karimov, and later Sh. Mirziyoyev, supported all-round ties with the United States. For Uzbekistan, the objectives of cooperation include the expansion of trade, investment and technology transfer, security assistance, including training in defense, supply of military equipment and support in the fight against terrorism; diplomatic approval and recognition of Uzbekistan's domestic achievements and international interests, as well as maintaining a significant US presence in the balance of other external forces. The Washington's list of priorities for cooperation with Tashkent included combating terrorism, countering to proliferation of weapons of mass

destruction, supporting stability in Afghanistan, ensuring the sovereignty and autonomy of Uzbekistan, developing bilateral economic ties and improving human rights.

D. Trump's support for US foreign policy based on realistic principles and the establishment of priorities for national sovereignty is consistent with the position of Uzbekistan under the leadership of Sh. Mirziyoyev. The prospects for improving relations between the United States and Uzbekistan during Trump's presidency may have strengthened the position of Tashkent's non-participation in Eurasian integration projects under the leadership of Moscow, such as the Collective Security Treaty Organization and the Eurasian Economic Union.

On 19 December, 2017, the presidents of the United States and Uzbekistan discussed regional security, economic reforms in Uzbekistan and other "opportunities for improving cooperation". The Government of Uzbekistan stressed that Trump welcomed the development of his productive relations with neighboring countries and supported the democratic changes and economic reforms taking place in the country aimed at strengthening civil society, the rule of law and economic liberalization.

Business development and improving the business environment

Our country's increasingly hasty and transparent policy is paving the way for a new level of relations with advanced skills. President **Mirziyoyev** agreed to create favourable conditions for business in Uzbekistan and open their markets to US companies and investors. In addition, **Uzbekistan and the United States** have signed more than 20 major contracts worth **\$ 4.8 billion (38 trillion Uzbek soums)** if fully implemented (Putz, 2020). The number of jobs created as a result has yet to be calculated, but some American companies have announced new projects. On May 15, Jizzakh Petroleum of Uzbekistan and Honeywell UOP of the United States signed licensing and engineering contracts to construct an oil refinery in the Jizzakh region, which will process 5 million tons of oil per year. On May 16, US General Electric announced that it had signed a

contract with Uzbekenergo to build a 660-megawatt unit at the Tashkent Thermal Power Plant. During Mirziyoyev's visit, the Uzbek Foreign Trade Ministry signed various agreements with American partners (Kun. UZ, 2021). In particular, the US company WCC (Public & Private Employment Services and government ID/Security agencies) International has agreed to implement a joint project to ensure uninterrupted access to Uzbek products in the US market. The plan is to promote such products on electronic platforms, especially Amazon. "We have made some progress in this regard," Uzbek Foreign Trade Minister Jamshid Khodjaev said in a **May 17** statement aimed to further develop Uzbekistan's economy.

At the end of January 2021, goods and services from 114 countries were imported to the Republic of Uzbekistan. A ninth of imports (200 million US dollars) is accounted for by such large partner countries as the USA (share in the total imports of 12.0%), the Russian Federation (19.9%), Kazakhstan (12.7%), Turkey (6.6%), France (4.9%), Republic of Korea (4.4%) and Lithuania (2.8%):

GEOGRAPHY OF EXPORT OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLES
(for January 2021)

Countries	thousand tons	million US dollars	specific weight, %*
Kazakhstan	23,6	8,1	19,8
PRC	9,9	7,6	18,7
Russian Federation	9,3	7,3	17,8
Kyrgyzstan	4,8	3,7	9,0
Afghanistan	3,6	3,0	7,5
Pakistan	3,1	3,0	7,4
Azerbaijan	1,4	1,2	3,0
Turkey	0,8	0,8	2,0
USA	0,2	0,7	1,7
Turkmenistan	2,4	0,7	1,7

Taking the U.S.-Uzbekistan Relationship to the Next Level: Mirziyoyev's Historic Visit

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's visit to Washington was historic, being the first official visit of an Uzbek president since 2002. Mirziyoyev's reception, and the breadth and width of agreements signed, constitute an acknowledgement of the reform process in Uzbekistan, as well as of the country's newfound regional role and in particular its constructive approach to resolving the problem of Afghanistan. Washington's engagement in these efforts will further improve the prospects of success in Uzbekistan's domestic reforms and regional initiatives.

The official visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, to the United States of America in May 2018 has been characterized as historic. Indeed, the Uzbek leader's meetings at the White House, Congress, with key departments, major corporations and international financial institutions indicate that this visit brought significant results. President Mirziyoyev received a warm welcome in Washington,

being accompanied with the highest level of Diplomatic protocol and being accorded significant time by U.S. President Donald Trump. Following the negotiations conducted in Washington DC, the two Presidents issued a Joint Declaration, “The United States and Uzbekistan: Launching a New Era of Strategic Partnership.” A package of documents was signed during the visit, to include protocols to enlarge bilateral trade relations and cooperation in higher education and academic research, agricultural industry and energy. A memorandum of understanding was signed to establish cooperation in Uzbekistan’s bid to join the World Trade Organization (WTO) and to organize a Central Asian Trade Forum in 2018 in Tashkent. Another Memorandum was signed between Uzbekistan’s National Bank of Foreign Economic Activity and the U.S. Export-Import Bank to finance cooperative projects. Corporations of the two countries signed more than 20 large contracts estimated to be worth \$4.8 billion. In the sphere of security, the U.S. and Uzbekistan agreed on a five-year plan in defense and military affairs targeted at consolidation of peace and stabilization in the region. At the World Bank headquarters, World Bank Group President Jim Yong Kim praised Uzbekistan’s reform process and loan agreements for \$940 million were signed, with the purpose of financing project in energy efficiency, horticulture, and emergency medical services. The total World Bank engagement up to 2020 includes 27 significant projects, with a total worth exceeding \$4 billion. In addition, an agreement on consulting services was signed with International Financial Corporation (IFC), focused on improving public-private partnerships to attract private investors to Uzbekistan.

An important result of the Uzbek leader’s official visit to the United States is Washington’s support for Tashkent’s initiatives concerning Afghanistan. If President Mirziyoyev’s proposals are implemented – including mechanisms of consultations of among heads of Central Asian states, and the economic, social and cultural integration of Afghanistan into this region – this would undoubtedly facilitate efforts to overcome

the Afghan crisis and create conditions for Central and South Asian development over time. Today, new leaders are in charge in Uzbekistan and the U.S., and are taking a fresh attitude to world and regional affairs. This provides promising prospects for the further deepening of relations between the two sides, based on their common aspiration to maintain peace and stability, and to improve mutually beneficial and long term relationships. These mutual interests formed the agenda of highest level Uzbek-American negotiations, whose success indicate a positive bilateral understanding. This inspires confidence that Washington and Tashkent will implement these agreements promptly and efficiently, benefiting both their own citizens and all states in the region. In 2024, the trade turnover between Uzbekistan and the United States increased by 15 percent, reaching \$881.7 million. The volume of direct investments from the United States amounted to \$612.6 million. Currently, there are 314 enterprises in Uzbekistan with the participation of American capital, of which American investors wholly own 167. These data were announced at the Uzbekistan American Business Forum, held as part of the Tashkent International Investment Forum at the capital's CAEx Exhibition Complex. This prestigious event was organized by the Ministry of Investment, Industry and Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the American – Uzbekistan Chamber of Commerce. Representatives of the business circles of the two countries attended the event.

The Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan Jamshid Khodjayev, Chairman of the Board of the American – Uzbekistan Chamber of Commerce Carolyn Lamm, First Deputy Chairman of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis Sodiq Safoyev and others addressed the event, stressing that cooperation between the two countries contributes to the expansion of economic potential.

“This event is a significant milestone in the history of bilateral economic relations between Uzbekistan and the United States. In recent years, Uzbekistan’s economy has

almost doubled. In 2024, the growth rate was 6.5 percent. More than \$6 billion of foreign direct investment was attracted. As part of the Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy, the goal is to increase GDP to \$200 billion, investments to \$100 billion, and exports to \$45 billion. Uzbekistan has sustained economic growth, with industry growing by an average of 8 percent per year. The volume of exports has doubled”, Mr. Khodjayeve noted. He also stressed that Uzbekistan is located in the Central Asian region, with a population of 83 million people and a free trade regime with extensive markets, the total number of which reaches 300 million people. More than 6,200 types of products are exported to the European market through the GSP+ system. Over the past year, exports have increased by 27 percent.

In recent years, relations between Uzbekistan and the United States of America have gained a new impetus. Moving beyond formal diplomacy, the partnership has evolved into a deeper, multi-dimensional engagement. Today, political dialogue is active, economic and business ties are expanding, and humanitarian and people-to-people connections are steadily strengthening.

Until 2017, Uzbek-American cooperation was primarily focused on regional security issues and the situation in Afghanistan, while noticeable progress in the economy and investment was virtually absent. However, following the election of Shavkat Mirziyoyev and his visit to Washington in 2018, cooperation began to acquire a strategic character. This marked the first visit by an Uzbek leader to the United States in 16 years and signaled a new level of mutual trust. During the visit, agreements and memoranda totaling over \$4.8 billion were signed, paving the way for projects involving major U.S. companies. These positive trends have largely been driven by Uzbekistan's domestic reforms and its pragmatic approach to regional and foreign policy. Consequently, diplomatic engagement has intensified: regular consultations at the level of foreign ministries have fostered systematic and structured cooperation.

Since the 2020s, relations have evolved into a multi-layered structure. In 2021, the format of political consultations was transformed into the "**Strategic Partnership Dialogue between Uzbekistan and the United States**," encompassing the economy, security, and environmental issues. The first meeting of this new format took place in Tashkent and laid the foundation for comprehensive cooperation.

In 2024, bilateral relations reached a qualitatively new level with the official establishment of an **expanded strategic partnership**. This format is based on the alignment of key priorities: Uzbekistan seeks deep economic modernization, attraction of foreign investment, integration into global markets, and the formation of a competitive economy.

The United States supports these efforts, affirming its commitment to the reform process and encouraging American business participation in the new opportunities emerging in Uzbekistan. To increase the export of Uzbek goods to the U.S., the President instructed the regions of the country to establish direct connections with individual states. For instance, in August of this year, a task was set to increase textile exports to the U.S. five to sixfold. Within this initiative, the **Andijan Region Textile Trade House** opened a representative office in **St. Louis**, one of the country's key logistics hubs.

Furthermore, American investment companies are showing significant interest in regional development. For example, the American investment company **Oppenheimer** will finance three large projects worth **\$1.2 billion** in the Andijan region, including the creation of a textile industrial zone (\$180 million), the construction of an artificial lake in Khanabad (\$20 million), and the "New Andijan" urban development project (\$1 billion).

Following this, in October 2024, a U.S. delegation led by President Biden's Special Envoy for South and Central Asia, **Sergio Gor**, and Deputy Secretary of State **Christopher Landau** visited Tashkent. The visit reinforced mutual trust and

underscored both sides' commitment to advancing joint initiatives in key areas of the bilateral agenda.

Undoubtedly, the U.S. contribution to Uzbekistan's economy maintains a steady dynamic: in 2024, trade turnover increased by 15%, reaching \$881.7 million. The portfolio of investment projects exceeds \$11 billion. These figures illustrate a steady expansion of trade and economic cooperation, even as overall volumes remain relatively modest.

At the same time, the contemporary economic agenda extends beyond traditional trade. Joint industrial and investment projects, collaboration in logistics, civil aviation, the agro-industrial complex, and metallurgy, as well as the implementation of digital and innovative solutions in supply chain management, are coming to the forefront.

The United States remains the largest market for Uzbek IT services: of 800 active exporters, 448 provide digital services to the U.S., representing 45% of total IT exports. This underscores the U.S.'s role as a strategic partner in Uzbekistan's technology sector. Uzbekistan has once again attracted U.S. attention due to the presence of **critically important minerals and rare earth elements** used in batteries, semiconductors, and modern defense systems. In April 2025, the countries signed an agreement on cooperation in the extraction of such resources, and in September, the American investor **Cove Capital** began geological exploration work.

Significant progress is also observed in the humanitarian sphere: the number of academic exchanges and educational programs is increasing, and the interest of Uzbek youth in American education has noticeably grown. Currently, 40 Uzbek universities implement partnership projects with more than 25 American universities and educational institutions. Cooperation includes academic exchange of faculty and students, joint research, and the engagement of American specialists in the educational process.

These initiatives reflect Uzbekistan's aspiration for greater openness and integration into the international community, creating conditions to expand contacts in tourism and cultural fields. In this context, **starting January 1, 2026, Uzbekistan will introduce a 30-day visa-free regime for U.S. citizens.** Previously, such a regime only applied to tourists over 55 years old. The new rules significantly facilitate U.S. citizens' access to the country, promoting tourism, business travel, and cultural exchanges, as well as opening additional opportunities for establishing direct contacts between individuals and organizations in both countries.

U.S.-Uzbekistan bilateral trade data from official sources shows steady growth, with opportunities in key sectors like textiles and agriculture amid Uzbekistan's WTO push. Recent reports highlight a U.S. trade surplus and rising services trade. Below are key tables summarizing volumes, trends, and top products.

Goods Trade Volumes (2024)

Year	U.S. Exports (\$M)	U.S. Imports (\$M)	U.S. Balance (\$M)
2024	380.7	42.4	338.3
2023	343.3	95.3	-

Total two-way goods trade reached \$423.1 million in 2024, up from prior years, with exports growing 10.9%.

Top Products (2023)

U.S. Exports to Uzbekistan: Cars (\$119M), aircraft (\$40M), vehicle parts (\$27.2M).
Uzbekistan Exports to U.S.: Silver (\$32.6M), copper wire (\$26.7M), refined petroleum (\$24.1M).

Annual Goods Trade (2020-2024)

Year	U.S. Exports	U.S. Imports	Balance
2020	181.1	80.7	100.4
2021	401.3	187.4	214.0
2022	271.0	59.0	212.0
2023	343.3	95.3	248.0
2024	380.7	42.4	338.3

Exports rose 110% from 2020 to 2024, while imports fell 47% in the same period.

The analysis shows that trade between Uzbekistan and the United States has increased gradually in recent years. Nevertheless, the total volume of bilateral trade remains small compared to Uzbekistan's trade with other partners such as China, Russia, and the European Union.

Uzbekistan's exports to the U.S. are mainly concentrated in textiles and apparel. This reflects the country's strong position in cotton production and the development of textile manufacturing. Some agricultural products, including dried fruits, are also exported but in limited quantities.

Imports from the United States mainly include machinery, equipment, chemical products, and technology-intensive goods. These imports contribute to industrial modernization and productivity growth in Uzbekistan.

At the same time, several factors limit trade expansion. Long geographical distance increases transportation costs. Strict quality and certification requirements in the U.S. market create difficulties for Uzbek exporters. Limited information about the U.S. market also affects export performance.

Conclusion

This study shows that trade relations between Uzbekistan and the United States remain underdeveloped but have strong potential for future growth. Recent economic reforms in Uzbekistan, including trade liberalization and support for the private sector, have created more favorable conditions for expanding bilateral trade. However, these opportunities have not yet been fully realized.

The analysis indicates that Uzbekistan's exports to the U.S. market are still highly concentrated, mainly in the textile and apparel sector. While this reflects positive progress in value-added production, it also highlights the limited diversification of exports. Expanding exports of agricultural products, processed foods, and services could help reduce dependence on a narrow range of goods and strengthen trade sustainability. The study also identifies several key challenges that limit trade expansion. These include strict regulatory and quality standards in the U.S. market, high transportation and logistics costs, and limited access to market information for Uzbek exporters. Small and medium-sized enterprises face particular difficulties in meeting certification requirements and entering the U.S. market.

Based on these findings, several policy recommendations can be proposed. First, exporter support programs should be strengthened to improve awareness of U.S. market requirements and standards. Second, investment in logistics infrastructure and trade facilitation measures should be increased to reduce transportation costs and delivery times. Third, greater attention should be given to the development of services trade, especially in information technology, education, and professional services, which offer new opportunities for bilateral cooperation.

Overall, strengthening trade relations between Uzbekistan and the United States is of strategic importance. Deeper trade cooperation can contribute not only to economic growth but also to technology transfer, institutional development, and long-term

economic diversification. Future research should focus on sector-specific analyses and examine how global economic and geopolitical developments may influence bilateral trade relations.

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